

A New Approach to Quantifying Vessel Form and Defining Types through Profile Syntax

Marko Porčić; Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia;
mporcic@f.bg.ac.rs; ORCID: 0000-0002-6697-8621

Mihailo Radinović; Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia;
ORCID: 0000-0001-5313-5548

Aleksandra Jovanić; Faculty of Fine Arts, University of Arts in Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia;
ORCID: 0000-0002-3496-4962

Abstract

The classification of ceramic vessels has long been central to archaeological analysis, yet traditional visual typologies remain subjective, difficult to replicate, and highly sensitive to observer expertise. Numerical approaches derived from geometric morphometrics (GM) offer greater objectivity, but they often fail to capture archaeologically meaningful aspects of form, particularly the syntax of vessel profiles which is defined here as the ordered sequence of rising, falling, concave, and convex segments that shape the vessel outline. Because GM methods primarily quantify proportions and global outline similarity, they may overlook syntactic configurations that human observers readily perceive and use to define and replicate types in the process of cultural transmission. This paper introduces a new quantitative method explicitly designed to capture vessel-profile syntax through analysis of the first and second derivatives of profile curves. By conceptualizing the vessel outline as a mathematical function, the method uses derivative-based measures to identify local geometric behavior and divide the profile into syntactic segments. Each segment is then paradigmatically classified, resulting in discrete formal categories that can be combined to generate “absolute” vessel types defined independently of sample composition. Applied to a set of twenty virtual vessels, the method successfully reproduces visually defined types and reveals syntactical variation not detectable through standard GM procedures. We also demonstrate the method on a set of 28 Early Iron Age vessel profiles. Because the approach relies on pseudolandmark data derived from scanned drawings, it enables full automation and high-throughput analysis, allowing large datasets to be processed efficiently. While the method does not replace existing geometric morphometric techniques, as it is blind to variation in overall size and

proportion, it provides a complementary framework for systematically quantifying vessel form.

Keywords: vessel classification; geometric morphometrics; types; archaeological systematics; vessel syntax.

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1. Introduction

The classification of vessels into types based on their form has long been one of the central concerns of archaeological research (Read 2007). Vessels are most commonly ceramic; however, comparable classificatory issues occur with other materials. The range of purposes for which classifications (or “typologies”) are constructed is extensive: measuring time (for example, through seriation or stratigraphic analysis of type distributions), examining interaction among communities across space, exploring expressions of identity, and distinguishing between vessel functions, to name only a few.

Archaeological classifications of ceramic vessels have traditionally relied on visual inspection and expert judgment. Such approach is highly sensitive to the observer’s perception and is often capable of capturing subtle similarities and differences in the vessel form when performed by experts. However, this approach is also subjective, difficult to replicate, and usually requires a comprehensive revision of the typological system whenever new specimens are added.

To address the limitations of traditional approaches to artefact classification, archaeologists turned to quantitative methods, an extensive array of techniques grouped under the banner of numerical taxonomy (Baxter 1994; Baxter 2003; Clarke 1968; Doran and Hodson 1975; Shennan 2004) and geometric morphometrics (Cardillo 2010; Elewa 2010; Okumura and Araujo 2019), which are generally regarded as more objective and reproducible (for a detailed and insightful review of classification in archaeology, see Read 2007). When combined with modern technologies such as 3D scanning of vessels or 2D scanning of profile drawings and photographs, quantitative approaches offer the potential for automation and high-throughput analysis (e.g. Barceló 2010; Demján et al. 2023; Kampel and Zambanini 2015; Karasik and Smilansky 2011; Košťál et al. 2025; Lenardi and Merwin 2010; Loftus 2022; Martínez-Carrillo et al. 2010; Pyzel and Suhrbier 2024; Radinović and Krečković Gavrilović 2023; Wang and Marwick 2020).

However, quantitative methods of classification also have their limitations. Many of these approaches similarly require reclassification when the dataset is expanded. For example, cluster analysis or principal component analysis based on metric variables must be rerun each time a new vessel is added.

More importantly, methods of numerical taxonomy are not necessarily sensitive to those aspects of form that are archaeologically meaningful. This is often the case with methods and techniques that are imported from other disciplines, such as geometric morphometrics, which is imported from biology (Okumura and Araujo 2019). Moreover, all methods for quantifying the properties of archaeological artefacts are essentially blind tools. Their usefulness depends on the extent to which the analyst succeeds in matching the archaeological concept of interest to its mathematical operationalization. In this paper, we identify one such problem in the standard geometric morphometric approach and propose a new method for quantifying an important aspect of vessel forms and using it to classify vessels into types.

The paper begins by outlining the theoretical foundations of archaeological classification and systematics (Dunnell 1971; O'Brien and Lyman 2000; Read 2007) in order to establish precise terminology, to clarify how classification operates and what kinds of general classificatory structures are possible. Next, a conceptual framework for analyzing vessel form is developed, and the limitations of the two standard geometric morphometric techniques for capturing key aspects of vessel morphology are demonstrated. The main part of the paper introduces a new method that successfully addresses these limitations. The method is demonstrated on a set of virtual and real-world prehistoric vessels.

2. Classification in archaeology: basic concepts

Dunnell (1971) distinguishes between taxonomy and classification proper. This distinction reflects the manner in which types or classes are constructed, either through extensional or intensional definitions of types, that is, through extensional (taxonomic) or paradigmatic classification, respectively (Dunnell 1971; O'Brien and Lyman 2000).

We begin with numerical taxonomy, as it is directly relevant to the subject of this study and represents a commonly employed form of taxonomy in archaeological systematics. Numerical taxonomy is based on the extensional definition of types. Consider, for example, one of its standard applications in archaeology: cluster analysis of metric variables measured on ceramic vessels (Figure 1). The analyst first records specific physical dimensions of

vessels, such as height and various diameters taken along the vessel profile. Using these measurements, a matrix of distances between objects is constructed. A clustering algorithm is then applied to this matrix to produce a dendrogram that represents taxonomy of the vessels. Finally, the analyst determines the height at which the dendrogram should be cut to generate groups, which are then interpreted as types. Such types are extensionally defined by enumerating the characteristics shared by the members of each group (e.g. statistical summaries of the metric variables for each cluster).

Figure 1. Schematic representation of performing numerical taxonomy by cluster analysis.

The resulting groups are typically polythetic because their defining characteristics may overlap (see Clarke 1968). There is no single set of necessary and sufficient conditions for membership. Since the definition of types depends on the contents of the matrix of pairwise distances among vessels, any addition or removal of specimens alters the taxonomic structure and, consequently, redefines the types themselves as group composition and diagnostic features shift. Thus, this mode of type construction is inherently dependent on the specific set of objects being classified, and the resulting taxonomy is not stable. Typologies produced through numerical-taxonomic methods can be considered relative, as they depend on the specific set of objects being classified and on the arbitrary choice of where to cut the clustering dendrogram.

In contrast, paradigmatic classification is based on the intensional definition of types, in which types correspond to the intersections of dimension values used to characterize objects (O'Brien and Lyman 2000; Dunnell 1971). For example, if we measure the height and width of vessels and discretize each variable by dividing it into two equal *a priori* selected intervals

(e.g., low – between 10 and 20cm, and high – between 20cm and 50cm), we obtain four possible classes (types) to which individual vessels may belong (Table 1):

	Width between 5cm and 10cm	Width between 10cm and 20cm
Height between 10cm and 20cm	Type 1 (low width and high height)	Type 2 (high width and high height)
Height between 20cm and 50cm	Type 3 (low width and low height)	Type 4 (low width and high height)

Table 1. Hypothetical paradigmatic classification of objects based on dichotomized height and width.

Types generated through paradigmatic classification are ideational units, whereas those produced by numerical taxonomy represent empirical units (O'Brien and Lyman 2000). Consequently, typologies derived from paradigmatic classification can be considered absolute, because their definitions do not depend on empirical groupings of objects.

3. Two aspects of vessel form: proportions and profile syntax

The concept of vessel form or shape seems intuitive and self-explanatory but it is not a unidimensional phenomenon (Read 2007: 149-157). We distinguish between two aspects of vessel form:

1. Proportions of the vessel, referring to the ratios between selected metrical attributes such as height, width, and various diameters. For example, vessels may be classified as narrow or wide based on the ratio between maximum width and height. If the overall size of a vessel changes while its proportions remain the same, this aspect of vessel form has not been altered.
2. The second aspect of the vessel form is its geometric syntax. The vessel syntax refers to how elementary profile segments, such as concave/convex and rising/falling sections, are organized into a complete vessel shape. It represents an ordered sequence of morphometric segments forming the vessel profile. This concept is similar to Read's (2007: 151) concept of "constructed geometrical shape differences".

It can be argued (but ultimately it would have to be tested) that the syntax is the most salient aspect of vessel form, as human observers readily recognize recurrent syntactic configurations in vessel profiles, and these configurations often correspond to emic or analytic types (cf. Read 2007: 95-106). This observation motivates the development of a procedure that can translate these perceptual criteria into a formal, quantitative framework. Yet, the standard methods of vessel form analysis such as pseudolandmark, semi-landmark or elliptical Fourier analysis of outlines may sometimes miss this aspect of the vessel form.

4. An example of how standard geometric morphometric methods may fail to capture vessel syntax

To illustrate this point, consider a set of virtual vessels¹ presented in Figure 2. The human eye readily groups them into four general types on the basis of the vessel syntax – each type represented by 5 vessels with the vessels of the same type in each row in Figure 2.

Figure 2. A set of virtual vessels (2D projection of 3D models); vessels in each row belong to one of four types identified by visual analysis.

¹ The virtual vessels were created using a software developed with p5.js (a free and open-source JavaScript library based on the Processing programming environment syntax - <https://p5js.org/>).

Let us now consider the results obtained when we quantify their profile outlines using geometric morphometrics and then apply numerical taxonomy to identify types (data and R code are available in Online Resources 1 and 2). We use two commonly used methods in geometric morphometry to show how they may fail to detect differences in profile syntax – pseudolandmark approach and elliptical Fourier analysis (Caple et al. 2017; Claude 2008).

4.1. The pseudolandmark approach

The profiles of the virtual vessels from Figure 2 were first proportionally scaled to same height (files with scaled vessel outlines are available in Online Resource 1²). This standardization step allows the subsequent analysis to focus exclusively on variation in profile form rather than on absolute dimensions.

After rescaling, the outline of each vessel profile was sampled at equidistant intervals of one pixel along the height of the vessel. At every horizontal slice, a single point was extracted from the outline such that the sequence of points captured the curvature of the vessel continuously from rim to base. This procedure ensured that all vessels were described by the same number of outline points, located at equidistant positions along the profile – the pseudolandmarks (Claude 2008: 205).

For each pseudolandmark point, the horizontal distance to the vertical axis of symmetry of the vessel was measured. This produced, for every vessel, a one-dimensional shape descriptor representing how far the profile deviates from the midline at each height. This curve was smoothed using a loess function.

The final dataset takes the form of an $n \times p$ matrix, where $n = 20$ is the number of vessels, and $p = 946$ is the number of equidistant outline points sampled along each profile. In this matrix, each row corresponds to a vessel, and each column corresponds to the deviation of the profile from the axis of symmetry at a specific height position – the profile form curve. This means that each vessel is represented as a point in a 946-dimensional space, where each dimension

² The data and R code associated with this study are openly available in the Zenodo repository at <https://zenodo.org/records/20705464> (DOI number: 10.5281/zenodo.20705464).

corresponds to the distance of a specific point along the vessel's profile from its axis of vertical symmetry.

Principal component analysis was applied to this data matrix, and cluster analysis (using Ward's method) was performed on the matrix of pairwise Euclidean distances between vessel profile curves. The results of the PCA are presented in Figure 3. The first and second principal components account for 79.56% and 11.56% of the variance, respectively. Although vessels assigned to the same type (as established by visual analysis) sometimes cluster together in the principal component space, the separation of visually defined types is far from perfect. Results of the cluster analysis (Figure 4) are consistent with the PCA results. The resulting clusters in most cases consist of vessels belonging to different visually established types.

Figure 3. Results of the principal component analysis of vessel profile curves. Colors indicate the type to which each vessel was assigned based on visual inspection.

Figure 4. Results of the cluster analysis performed on the matrix of pairwise Euclidean distances between vessel profile curves. Colors indicate the type to which each vessel was assigned based on visual inspection.

We can see that the numerical taxonomy based on the pseudolandmark approach fails to reproduce the visually established types which clearly reflect the syntactical aspect of the form. In fact, the first principal component can be interpreted as representing the relative width of a vessel, with relatively wide vessels placed toward the negative end of the axis and relatively narrow vessels toward the positive end. In other words, the first principal component based on the numerical description of the profile curve primarily captures variation in vessel proportion, rather than variation in vessel syntax.

4.2. Elliptical Fourier analysis

In addition to the pseudolandmark approach, we also performed an elliptical Fourier analysis (EFA) on the outlines of the 20 virtual vessels shown in Figure 2. EFA is one of the most sophisticated methods of geometric morphometry with increasing number of applications in archaeology (Cardillo 2010; García-Bustos et al. 2024; Hoggard et al. 2019; Loftus 2022; Radinović and Kajtez 2021; Riede et al. 2019; Wang and Marwick 2020).

We implemented elliptical Fourier analysis (EFA) using the Momocs package in R (Bonhomme et al. 2014; Claude 2008). Twenty harmonics were extracted from the outlines, and principal component analysis (PCA) was subsequently applied to the resulting coefficients (the R code for the analysis is available in Online Resource 3). Twenty harmonics captured at least 99.7% of harmonic power for all vessels, indicating that this number of harmonics is sufficient to accurately represent vessel outlines. The results are presented in Figure 5. The EFA appears to perform somewhat better than the pseudolandmark

approach in separating the visually identified types; however, the separation is not complete, as overlap between types remains in the space defined by the first two principal component axes.

Figure 5. Plot of the PC axis 1 and PC axis 2 scores of the 20 vessel outlines based on the results of the EFA analysis with 20 harmonics.

5. Quantifying profile syntax: a derivative-based approach

To address this limitation, we propose the method which aims to formalize and quantify precisely the syntactical features of vessel form that human observers detect intuitively. If a vessel profile is conceptualized as a mathematical curve, then the essential information about its local geometric behavior is contained in its derivatives or their mathematical transformations (Karasik and Smilansky 2011). The first derivative indicates whether the curve is increasing or decreasing at any point, while the second derivative distinguishes concave from convex regions (Figure 6). Taken together, these two derivatives provide a complete description of the vessel syntax.

Figure 6. Schematic illustration showing how the first (f') and second (f'') derivatives of the vessel profile function encode information about vessel shape syntax.

5.1. Defining types using numerical taxonomy

Accordingly, the proposed method applies the pseudolandmark procedure not to the raw profile itself, but to the curves which represent the first and second derivatives of the original profile curve. This reparameterization recasts the analysis from one focused on proportions to one focused on local shape syntax. We will illustrate this on the example of the vessel profiles from Figure 2. The analysis consists of the following steps (the height-scaled vessel outline drawings and the R code are given in Online Resource files 1 and 2):

1. Vessels were first scaled to a uniform height.
2. Vessel outlines are smoothed using the loess function.

3. The first and second derivatives of the vessel profile curves were computed – approximated by difference equations (Figure 7).
4. Equidistant (1-pixel) outline points, the pseudolandmarks, were placed along each derivative curve.
5. For every point along the vessel profile, the values of the first and second derivatives at that location were recorded.
6. This procedure produced two data matrices of size $n \times p$, one for each derivative, where $n = 20$ is the number of vessels and $p = 946$ is the number of outline points.
7. The two matrices were merged into a single $n \times 2p$ matrix by column-wise concatenation, combining both curvature (first derivative) and curvature-change (second derivative) information.
8. Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed on the merged matrix to reduce dimensionality and summarize major axes of variation.
9. Cluster analysis was applied to the Euclidean distance matrix computed from the full set of principal components (40) obtained from the previous step, ensuring that distances reflect variation captured in both derivatives of the vessel profiles.

Figure 7. An example of the profile curve and the first and second derivatives curve of one of the vessels from Figure 2.

The results of the PCA and cluster analyses based on the profile data from the virtual vessels are presented in Figures 8 and 9. Both methods clearly and accurately discriminate among the visually defined types, which correspond to distinct vessel shape syntax. When the dendrogram is cut to produce a four-cluster solution, the resulting clusters correspond exactly

to the visually defined types based on vessel syntax.

Figure 8. Results of the principal component analysis applied to the merged data matrices containing the first and second derivative values of the vessel profile curve at each pseudolandmark point. Colors indicate the type to which each vessel was assigned based on visual inspection.

Figure 9. Results of the cluster analysis applied to the Euclidean distance matrix computed from the full set of principal components derived from the concatenated first- and second-derivative matrices. Colors indicate the type to which each vessel was assigned based on visual inspection.

5.2. Paradigmatic classification of vessel profile segments based on derivatives of the vessel profile curve – generating absolute types based on form syntax

The main contribution of the derivative-based method is that it enables the construction of “absolute” types grounded in the syntactical properties of vessel form. The types are labeled as absolute because their definition does not depend on the specific assemblage of objects that are classified. As such, they conform to Read's observation:

"Absolute qualitative and geometric differences are not context specific and do not depend on first identifying an artifact dimension or variable for defining the qualitative characteristic. An object can be assigned to a topological or geometric type solely by reference to the characteristics of the object in question and does not require a reference population to identify the type." (Read 2007: 299)

Defining types through paradigmatic classification of vessel segments is not new. For example, this is precisely the approach taken by Shennan and colleagues in their large-scale analysis of prehistoric pottery in Europe:

“Shape is recorded as a unique combination of 9 basic geometric forms (each an ellipsoid of revolution, e.g. a hyperboloid), with four bottom shapes (electronic online supplement figure S1 below) ... The resulting number of possible shapes (online supplement table S3) is a function of the observed material record, and in our specific case we identified 142 unique combinations of these forms and diagnostic types.”

(Shennan et al. 2015: Electronic Online Supplement Material S1; see also their Figure S1)

The method we propose is identical in principle to that of Shennan et al. (2015), but with one important difference: it does not rely on visual inspection of profile drawings. Instead, it uses a geometric morphometric representation of vessel form, quantified through the first and second derivatives of the profile curve. This shifts the basis of paradigmatic type definition from visually recognized segments to systematically measured syntactical structure. This enables more objective and automated classification into types. The method consists of the

following steps (the detailed implementation of the method is presented in the Online Resource 4 with the R code³ given in the Online Resource 5):

1. The digitized profile is smoothed using a smoothing spline.
2. For each point along the profile curve, an approximation of the first and second derivative at that point is calculated via difference equations.
3. Vessel is divided into segments based on the local minima/maxima of the profile curve and the inflection points of the second derivative (see Kampel and Zambanini 2015: Figure 2).
4. Each segment is described by two attributes: the dominant sign of the first derivative and the dominant sign of the second derivative. For each derivative, the dominant sign (positive, negative, or zero) is determined from the distribution and continuity of derivative values across all pseudolandmark points within the segment. This allows the segment to be classified according to its local slope and curvature. The technical details of the procedure for determining dominant derivative signs, as well as the full R implementation, are provided in Online Resources 4 and 5.
5. Each segment is paradigmatically classified into a discrete class based on the combination of values of the first and second derivatives according to the Table 2 below (see Figure 6 for visual reference):
6. The sequence of segment types represents the syntax of the vessel and it defines the vessel type. For example, if the vessel consists of three segments which are classified as B (decelerated increase), C (accelerated decrease) and D (decelerated decrease), the type code for the entire vessel is BCD (Figure 10). For technical reasons, the algorithm is implemented in a way that there is always one inflection point between two minima/maxima (except if the segment is extremely short), so it may happen that the segments divided by the inflection points belong to the same type. In this case, the type code is compressed, for example DAAF will be compressed to DAF.

³ ChatGPT 5.1 was used as an aid in writing the R code for the transformation of image files into appropriate form for the analysis and for the implementation of the syntactical classification algorithm.

7.	$f'' = 0$	$f'' > 0$	$f'' < 0$
$f' = 0$	X (flat)	/	/
$f' > 0$	R (linear increase)	A (accelerated increase, convex)	B (decelerated increase, concave)
$f' < 0$	F (linear decrease)	C (accelerated decrease, concave)	D (decelerated decrease, convex)

Table 2. Paradigmatic classification of vessel-profile segments based on the combined signs of the first and second derivatives, representing the dominant slope and curvature of each segment.

Figure 10. Examples of how the vessels are assigned to "absolute" types based on the paradigmatically classified profile curve segments.

The results of the classification of the 20 virtual vessels from Figure 2, obtained using the method described above, are presented in Figure 11. The first thing to note is that the number of types identified by the method exceeds the number of visually defined types. Types BC and BCDABCD correspond exactly to the visually defined types in the first and fourth rows of Figure 2. Types BCDA and DAC each contain four of the five vessels belonging to the corresponding visually defined types in the second and third rows of Figure 2. However, the method also identifies two additional types represented by single vessels. This occurs because the method is more sensitive—perhaps overly sensitive—to subtle differences in shape that are not easily detected by the human eye. Type BCD differs from BCDA in lacking an outward curvature in the foot. Type DACF differs from DAC in the shape of the lower conus: in DACF, the lower conus becomes linear toward the base, whereas in DAC it remains curved throughout.

Figure 11. Virtual vessels from Figure 2 classified into absolute types based on sequences of paradigmatically classified segments. Vessels scaled to same height.

5.3. Demonstrating the method on an archaeological example

In this section, we demonstrate the classification method based on profile syntax using a real-world archaeological case study: a set of 28 complete ceramic vessels (Figure 12, complete set of vessel outlines available in Online Resource 6) from the Early Iron Age site of Kalakača in Serbia, dated approximately between 950 and 750 BCE (Medović 1988).

Figure 12. Early Iron Age vessels from Kalakača (after Medović 1988: vessels 1-4, Table IX; vessels 5-10, Table X; vessels 11-16, Table XI; Vessels 17-22, Table XII; vessels 23-28, Table XV; photographs reproduced with the permission of the publisher).

The vessel profiles were extracted from the published photographs (Medović 1988: Tables IX, X, XI, XII, XV). The same software used to generate the hypothetical vessels in Figure 2 was also employed to model and outline the Kalakača vessels. Vessel profiles were manually traced (Figure 13) using Bézier curves (Mortenson 1999: 264-276). Each profile is represented as a continuous Bézier curve composed of three segments, defined by ten control points: four endpoints (marking the beginnings and ends of segments) and six intermediate tangent control points. All vessel outlines were proportionally scaled to the same height.

Figure 13. An example of how profile curves were generated from vessel photographs.

The results of the classification indicate the presence of nine syntactical types (Figure 14). In most cases, these types are visually coherent, although there are notable exceptions. For example, vessels 26 and 27 are bowls, whereas the other vessels assigned to the BC type are pots; nevertheless, they are grouped into a single type. Similarly, the DABC type appears to encompass two distinct morphological groups – globular jars and pots.

SYNTACTICAL TYPE

Figure 14. Classification of the Iron Age pottery into types based on profile syntax. Vessels scaled to same height.

This is not a limitation but an expected property of the method: it exclusively captures profile syntax and is insensitive to variation in size and proportion. Although these vessels share the same profile syntax, their proportions (and overall size) differ substantially, which leads us to perceive them as distinct types. A final classification should therefore incorporate additional aspects of shape beyond syntax.

In a real-world analytical context, vessels with different functions and great differences in height, such as pots and bowls, would not be assigned to the same type to begin with, and separate analyses would typically be conducted for each functional class. Here, however, they

are analyzed together in order to make a point that the syntax of a vessel, operationalized here as a particular sequence of convex and concave curves, may be independent of other aspects of shape and size.

One possible solution is to perform principal component analysis (PCA) on the pseudolandmark data (or even better on the derivatives) for vessels within a given syntactical type (e.g., BC or DABC). For instance, applying PCA to pseudolandmark data on vessels classified as type BC produces a clear separation along the first principal component (PC1), corresponding to differences in vessel proportions (Figure 15).

Figure 15. Results of the PCA analysis on pseudolandmark data on Iron Age vessels belonging to the type DBCA. Vessels scaled to same height.

Alternatively, the filtering criteria can be adjusted to exclude segments that are too short, or the classification scheme can be refined by introducing additional segment classes. In the present implementation, classification is based solely on the sign of the derivatives, although their magnitude could also be incorporated. Here, we demonstrate the effect of increasing the segment-length threshold from 1% (used in previous classification runs) to 5%. Under this criterion, segments shorter than 5% of the total profile length are excluded from classification. This filtering may provide a shortcut toward more intuitive solutions in cases where very short, unrepresentative segments are present.

The results of the filtered classification are shown in Figure 16. Visually, this solution is more coherent than the previous one. However, when vessels with markedly different proportions share the same profile syntax across most of the profile, filtering alone cannot resolve this issue. In such cases, the method correctly reflects the underlying similarity in syntactical structure. Consequently, syntactical types C, BC, and CD remain internally heterogeneous, containing vessels that differ substantially in proportion and size and therefore require further subdivision. This indicates that *post hoc* analysis of variability within syntactical types is unavoidable in the case that no previous limits were set on the size and proportion of the vessels being classified.

SYNTACTICAL TYPE

Figure 16. Classification of the Iron Age pottery into types based on profile syntax with the filter set to 5%. Vessels scaled to same height.

6. Discussion and conclusion

By focusing explicitly on the syntactic organization of vessel profiles, this derivative-based approach provides a means of capturing features of vessel form that conventional geometric morphometrics tends to overlook. It bridges the gap between human perceptual classification and quantitative statistical analysis. This fact is of great relevance in the context of cultural transmission research (Eerkens and Lipo 2007; Lycett 2015; Porčić 2023; Shennan 2002; Shennan 2011), as it can be hypothesized that the syntax of a vessel is what makes the large if not the most important part of the "memotype" of a vessel, which is transmitted by social learning. For example, in experimental studies undertaken by Gandon and colleagues, different types of vessels are defined primarily by the syntactical aspect of the shape – all geometric morphometric analyses were performed separately for each type (Gandon et al., 2018; Gandon et al., 2021; Gandon et al., 2014), reflecting the implicit assumption that types defined in this way are salient both for the researchers and for the potters who participated in the experiment. In other words, vessel syntax constitutes one of the culturally salient qualitative aspects of form that are important in the identification of types (Read 2007).

The key practical contribution of this method is that it enables full automation of the classification process, making it possible to generate and analyze large datasets on a scale that was previously impractical⁴. The input data in the form of vessel outlines, can now be obtained relatively quickly, either through scanning published drawings or through 3D scanning of the vessels themselves.

None of this should be taken to imply that the proposed method ought to replace standard geometric morphometric approaches. On the contrary, the method presented here cannot capture the full morphometric reality of vessels (it does not achieve the archival description of the artifacts *sensu* Read 2007) as it is designed to isolate a single specific aspect of the vessel form – the syntax. It is completely blind to variation in qualitative attributes (e.g.

⁴ With respect to its technical implementation and its potential for large-scale analysis of digitized profile drawings, the current version of the computer code which accompanies this paper should be regarded as a "proof of concept" rather than a finished product. Its principal limitation is that it can only process drawings that conform to a very specific input format in terms of centering, height, and resolution. In practice, this means that arbitrary scans or digital images must first be manually transformed into this standardized format before analysis. Developing code and software that can automatically transform into desired format any scanned profile drawing, regardless of its original orientation, scale, or resolution, would address this issue. This is fundamentally an engineering challenge rather than a conceptual one, but it remains an important technical limitation of the implementation of the method in this paper.

decoration, surface treatment, fabric etc.), topology, proportions and size (as demonstrated above in the case of the Iron Age pottery from Kalakača), all of which are important for defining and analyzing types. Rather than serving as a standalone tool, this method should be used in combination with other approaches. For instance, one might use the derivative-based procedure to paradigmatically define types grounded in vessel syntax, and then apply other morphometric techniques to examine shape variation within these syntactical types (see section 5.3 above).

When it comes to the description of the local geometry of the profile curve, our method is mathematically similar to that formulated by Karasik and Smilansky (2011), although their approach does not primarily or explicitly target profile syntax. Karasik and Smilansky use three mathematical functions to fully describe a vessel profile curve: the radius at point s along the profile, the tangent at point s , and the curvature at point s . The tangent and curvature represent mathematical transformations of the first and second derivatives, respectively. Consequently, these two functions encode essentially the same geometrical information as the first and second derivatives, namely the syntactical information embedded in the profile.

The method proposed by Karasik and Smilansky allows different weights to be assigned to the three functions when calculating morphometric distances between pairs of vessels. If the weight associated with the radius function, which captures vessel size and proportions, is set to zero, the analytical protocol of Karasik and Smilansky becomes broadly equivalent to our numerical taxonomic analysis based on the derivatives of the profile curves (Section 5.1).

Karasik and Smilansky's method is superior when the goal is to include all aspects of vessel form within a single analysis and to perform classification through numerical taxonomy. However, their approach does not explicitly segment syntax into discrete structural units; rather, it aims to capture overall morphological similarity instead of compositional structure. Our method, in contrast, extracts the discrete structural grammar of the vessel profile.

The key feature of our method, therefore, is that it targets syntax both explicitly and exclusively, transforming it into a categorical (qualitative) dimension. This distinction is important if one accepts Read's (2007) concept of artifact classification, according to which qualitative attributes take priority in the construction of types because they are more likely to encode information about emic categories.

However, there are several limitations inherent both to the method itself and to its particular technical implementation in this paper:

1. Although the types produced by the method are objective in the sense that they can be replicated consistently, the algorithm may be overly sensitive to subtle geometric variations for which the cultural or analytical significance is uncertain. This is evident in the results presented here: the two types represented by single vessels in Figure 10 are “real” insofar as they reflect genuine geometric differences in vessel profiles, yet these differences are so slight that they are effectively imperceptible to the human eye and may not be relevant to the maker or to the user. This issue can be addressed by introducing filters that instruct the algorithm to ignore such minor fluctuations. In fact, some of these filters are already incorporated into the present implementation (see Online Resource 4). However, this also means that the method requires human input and parameter choices, which inevitably influence the number and granularity of types that the algorithm identifies.
2. As it is, the method is limited to the complete vessel profiles, but theoretically it can be extended to partial profiles based on fragments.
3. The presence of handles or other elements which are added to the body of the vessel may require the modification of the algorithm – the researcher must decide whether to treat handles as a separate element or as a part of the profile curve. Choosing the latter may disregard what Read (2007: 150) refers to as the topological aspects of the shape.

Despite its limitations, the results presented here show that the derivative-based approach provides a replicable, scalable, and theoretically grounded tool for defining vessel-form types and for advancing archaeological systematics. The full potential of this method remains to be demonstrated through problem oriented empirical case studies of archaeological pottery and of vessels made from other materials. In principle, the approach is applicable to any class of material culture for which variation in the form of a 2D profile is meaningful, suggesting promising avenues for extending the method to additional categories of artefacts. Future work should therefore explore these broader applications.

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